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Dual vocational training for work: First experiences in Ecuador

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Abstract

This research addresses the first practical, conceptual and methodological experiences on the implementation of the dual vocational training in Ecuador. The main objective is to analyse the implementation of the Dual vocational training model of the “Comprehensive Child Development” degree offered by public technical and technological higher education institutes. The methodological approach is qualitative, and from the case study selected the paradigms of the actor-network theory and the grounded theory are combined. The preliminary results of this first evaluation process represent a paradigmatic change of traditional Ecuadorian higher education. We may say that the Ecuadorian dual training approach breaks with the conservative principle of the German dual model ‘student-institute-company’, as it looks for the professionalization of human talent in relation to the social programs of the government.

Keywords

dual training; professionalization; higher education; professional skills; comprehensive child development

1 Introduction

This research addresses the first conceptual and methodological experiences on the implementation of the dual vocational training in Ecuador on 2013. The public higher education system in Ecuador, at both technical and technological levels, has developed and implemented a new model of alternative education based on competencies called “Dual vocational training” (Homs, 2016), which aims to create better job opportunities for Ecuadorians. This model represents a paradigm shift from the traditional training in public technical and technological institutes, more than 30 years ago.

The main objective is to analyse the implementation of the Dual vocational training model of the “Comprehensive Child Development” degree offered by public technical and technological higher education institutes. The model was implemented for competency-based training, as part of the Project to Restructure Public Higher Technical and Technological Education in Ecuador.

This research is based on a qualitative and quantitative methodological approach. The case study combines ideas of the Actor-Network Theory, and the Grounded Theory. This study makes use of empirical research techniques such as triangulation for the analysis of information. This method will be based on comparing and interpreting areas of agreement and discrepancies among these sources about dual vocational training and competencies professional for work. The basic data collection instruments are semi-structured interviews, focus groups protocols and digital questionnaire.

The epistemic mapping of studies within the educational models of dual vocational training based on competencies in the Ecuadorian context represents a test-trial process, by which the best international practices are chosen for implementation. During the first stage, which

focused on information gathering and analysis, a holistic approach to the socio-technical construction of the Dual model was made.

The evidence provided by the first interviewees was then analysed. They agree that the Dual methodological process, has barely been introduced into the higher education system, and has not properly followed the German principles of the relationship “student – institute – company”. The implementation the “Comprehensive Child Development” degree rather breaks the principle of this German vocational training, by replacing the “company”, with government programs that are financed and managed by the government itself. A first approximation to the skills and competencies he or she has actually obtained, are the appraisal of results and assessment which the students apply it in the process of Dual vocational training

These Dual vocational programmes often respond to the government’s own educational, social and economic objectives, especially addressing the need for professionals specialised in early childhood care.

To conclude, a new form of investigative analysis which is proposed, combined the assumptions of the Grounded Theory (Strauss and Corbin, 2002) and the Actor-Network Theory (Latour, 1996) to understand the symbolic path of Dual vocational training in Ecuador. This analysis begins with the implementation of an academic degree that pursues the high quality of life, socially and productively, from a new teaching perspective: Dual learning, which seeks to improve people’s skills and their employability in work environments emphasising their specialisation and professionalization.

2 The dual vocational training as a new model inside the public higher education system in Ecuador

2.1 Exploratory phase: social and technical approaches of the dual model

Global demands invite us to re-think and provide a diagnosis of the subject-object practices from the context of modern thinking. Educational models in the area of dual training are no exception and posit us to reflect on from the academic field, in order to understand the reason why such models are accepted and implemented within the higher education systems. It can be argued that paradigmatic changes in terms of educational mobility, scholarships, science transmission and interchange, technology, and innovation in higher education have dynamized cooperation networks, while at the same time they have strengthened human talent in Latin America. One of such paradigmatic changes has been achieved in Ecuador.

For the last decade, the Ecuadorian government has invested in human talent training and specialization in different areas of knowledge. To this end, public policies aimed at quality and academic excellence were revised, modified and established in 2008. In 2010 a comprehensive reform of the Education law was made in order to assure equality, equity and free access to higher education, not only at the university level, but also including technical and technology institutes. Hence, technical, administrative, academic and research components of public and private institutions were reinforced.

Along with the higher education legislation reform, different higher education programs and projects were boosted, always taking into account the needs of the productive matrix of the country. In 2014 the National Secretariat for Higher Education, Science, Technology and Innovation (SENESCYT, for its acronym in Spanish) launched a project called ‘Reconversion of public sector technical and technological education.’ One of the main components of the project was the design of the dual training model, aimed at promoting theoretical and practical education for future professionals.

In 2015, as the reconversion project was on course, the Higher Education Council (CES, for its acronym in Spanish) approved the new rules of procedure for institutes and conserva-

toires, by its resolution RPC-SO-35-No.457-2015. For the first time in the higher education system of Ecuador the ‘Rule for careers and programs in dual modality’ was inscribed in 2016, according to resolution RPC-SO -31-No.585-2016.

In that same year, the National Assembly of Ecuador approved the ‘Organic Code of Social Economy of Knowledges, Creativity and Innovation.’ This new law reinforced and promoted the dual training by providing economic incentives, such as tax reductions for those public or private organizations that hired dual training students for their productive and service activities.

This socio-technical trajectory, from its basic notion of co-construction related to learning processes, rationalities, policies, and different actors’ strategies (Thomas, 2011), began to be regulated from a kind of public policy that unifies academic, social, economic and productive aspects. All of this was made under the support of the central government and the head of the government, who in particular, aimed at boosting the technical and technological dual professional training. Precisely, at that time a dual training proposal for the design of a technical career in Comprehensive Child Development (TDII, for its acronym in Spanish) was made; its objective was to specialize the human talent for care and education of early childhood.

2.2 Methodology

The methodological approach is qualitative, and from the case study selected the paradigms of the actor-network theory and the grounded theory are combined. From a theoretical and sensitive outlook, academic texts which include the principles of the systems and models of dual training were analyzed. This facilitated the elaboration of a questionnaire used in the semi-structured interview. This whole process was made under the validation and supervision of experts in theory and methodology.

Prior to the interviews, a mapping of key actors was carried out. It is important to mention that such actors do not only represent individuals or power groups (Tapella, 2007:3), but they were chosen by their chronological participation in the dual training proposal. In order to locate these actors, three aspects were taken into consideration: professional profile, decision-making level, and their direct involvement in the development and implementation of the dual proposal. A group of 12 people were selected, all of them belong to public and private organizations. The information that was collected coincides with two different moments: the reconversion project and the design of the technical career in TDII.

Once the interviews were made, they were transcribed and their content and elements were processed under the phases of categorization, coding, structuring and cross-checking the information. This was made with the purpose of formalizing the early approaches and interpretations that allow to establish theoretical and explanatory conclusions regarding the dual model, considering the implementation of the TDII career as a point of departure.

2.3 Analysis: results

The information collected acquires an inductive structural order for the interpretation of the results. The data was processed under a content analysis method in relation to the enunciation of the interviewee.

As an example, there are textual citation of the discursive references, which refer to the implementation of the dual professional training, departing from the TDII academic offer.

1. In the first theme block, the interviewees reveal an heterogenous enunciation in terms of their relation with the dual topic, as well as their participation in the design and implementation of the TDII career.

[...] I committed myself to the review of documents, even if that was not my work specialization [...] so, the best I could do was that, to start reading, to start asking, re-researching [...] in that way we could find out how to implement the dual training in Ecuador [...] (IA6, 2017)

2. In the second theme block -the social and technical trajectory of the dual model- the interviewees present a unanimous discursive characteristic, in which the dual training is represented as an emergent demand through the reconversion project. Here, the early childhood care was a priority for the central government.

[...] This was framed in the social public policy, in fact the president always said [...] that the best option, even in aspects related to childhood malnutrition [...] was prevention. This could only be reached with trained human talent [...] (IA1, 2017)

3. Finally, the third block points out that the design of the TDII career needs to be based on competencies for the potential implementation in public institutes. Here, the interviewees mention that:

[...] The TDII dual modality career aims at solving social problems, so it requires trained personnel to be incorporated to the CIBV (Children's Centres for Good Living projects) ...the workers to carry out their responsibilities based on the practice, but without academic foundations [...] (IA9, 2017)

[...] the competency-based design is fundamental, the approach given to this career [...] even if it is important to know the concepts of childhood care, the competencies are much more based on practice. (IA9, 2017)

Every informant agreed to respond to the government demands, in terms of professionalization of human talent, under a technical and technological dual perspective.

3 Concluding remarks

To follow the actors and their actions in order to understand the reality of the dual model (Callon, 1986; Latour y Woolgar, 1997; Latour, 1996) represents a change of paradigm in relation to the traditional training model in Ecuador. In fact, the voice of the interviewees -actors- has provided with a network and social and technical ensemble (Wiebe Bijker, 1995) among those who are involved in the dual model according to level of involvement, consensus, and power relations, all of this in the face of the technical and technological public higher education of the country, particularly in the area of social services.

From this context, we may say that the Ecuadorian dual training approach breaks with the conservative principle of the German dual model 'student-institute-company', as it looks for the professionalization of human talent in relation to the social programs of the government. In response, the technical career in Comprehensive Child Development was designed. However, there is still much to do regarding the methodological alignment in the field of professional competencies.

Finally, it is important to stress that this initial research stage does not aim at identifying the causes and effects of the new dual model in the Ecuadorian context. To the contrary, it states a new form to carry out research analysis, by proposing new theoretical and explanatory approaches to the dual model, based on the grounded theory (Strauss y Corbin, 2002) and the actor-network theory (Latour, 1996).

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Biographical notes

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